

Studies on the Thermodynamics of Cobalt Exchange on Na-Kaolinite and Na-Illite

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The ion-exchange equilibria of cobalt with Na-kaolinite and Na-illite was studied. The exchange isotherms indicated a lower affinity for cobalt as compared to sodium on both the clays. The affinity varied with temperature. Free energy, enthalpy and entropy generally supported the inferences drawn from the exchange isotherms.

COBALT and other basic cations have been shown by many authors to combine with a variety of soils and soil forming minerals. Their results have been discussed in terms of exchange reactions, complex formation and lattice penetration. The pH is one of the dominant factors controlling the distribution of an element into one of these forms. Many equations^{1,2} have been proposed to describe the ion exchange processes and measure their quantitative aspects. In this paper an attempt has been made to investigate the equilibrium exchange of sodium and cobalt in two important clay minerals viz., illite and kaolinite at a low pH. In view of the great importance of cobalt as a trace element in plant metabolism and animal nutrition it was considered useful to extend our earlier work on the thermodynamics of cobalt exchange to some other clay minerals viz., kaolinite and illite. The basis of the treatment have been the thermodynamic formulations of earlier workers^{3,4,5}.

Experimental

Both the clays were A.P.I. monomineralic samples. Kaolinite was from Bath, South Carolina and illite from Morris, Illinois, USA. The less than 2 μ clays were dispersed to sodium forms according to the method of Aldrich and Buchanan⁶. The concentration of the suspensions was adjusted to 1.5% (w/v) and a pH equal to 4 with dil HNO₃. The adjustment to a low pH became necessary to prevent hydrolysis, precipitation and hysteresis effects⁷. The CEC of kaolinite and illite at pH 4 as determined by the ammonium acetate method were 5.0 and 15.0 meq. per 100 g respectively. The exchanges were carried out at 25 \pm 0.1° and 50 \pm 0.1° in both the clay minerals as per the method described earlier^{8,11}. The suspensions were then centrifuged and cobalt estimated colorimetrically using 1-nitroso-2-naphthol as a colour reagent at 530 m μ and sodium by flame photometry. The corresponding concentrations of sodium in the clay phases were obtained by difference (CEC minus concentration of the cation

in the supernatant liquids) and that for cobalt from cobalt added minus cobalt in the supernatant liquids.

Evaluation of Thermodynamic Quantities

The reaction between the sodium clays and Co²⁺ can be represented by the equation

In terms of equivalent ion concentrations in the clay phases and the solutions the exchanges can be described by the equation⁹

The equivalent ionic fractions of cobalt in the kaolinite and illite phases and in the respective solutions were calculated from the expressions

$$\bar{X}_{\text{Co}} = \frac{\bar{C}_{\text{Co}}}{\bar{C}}, \quad X_{\text{Co}} = \frac{C_{\text{Co}}}{C},$$

$$\bar{X}_{\text{Na}} = \frac{\bar{C}_{\text{Na}}}{\bar{C}} \quad \text{and} \quad X_{\text{Na}} = \frac{C_{\text{Na}}}{C} \quad \dots (3)$$

In the dilute range of concentration studied by us the selectivity coefficients were (taking the ratio of activity coefficients as unity¹⁰) calculated from the equation

$$K_{\text{C}} = \frac{\bar{X}_{\text{Co}}(X_{\text{Na}})^2}{(X_{\text{Na}})^2 X_{\text{Co}}} \quad \dots (4)$$

and the thermodynamic equilibrium constant K from the equation¹¹

$$\ln K = (Z_{\text{A}} - Z_{\text{B}}) + \int_0^1 \ln K_{\text{Cd}} \bar{X}_{\text{Co}} \quad \dots (5)$$

The thermodynamic functions (ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS°) were then calculated by utilising the van't Hoff reaction isotherm for ΔG° , the van't Hoff isochore for ΔH° and the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation for ΔS° . The values are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1 THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR COBALT EXCHANGE WITH Na-KAOLINITE AND Na-ILLITE AT 25° AND 50°

Thermodynamic parameters	Exchange in kaolinite		Exchange in illite	
	25°	50°	25°	50°
K	0.188	0.242	0.111	0.100
ΔG° (cal/mole)	990.3	912.6	1304.6	1488.7
ΔH° (cal/mole)	1915.5		-761.2	
ΔS° (cal/mole)	3.1	3.1	-6.9	-6.9

Results and Discussion

From the values of equivalent ionic fractions at 25° and 50° calculated for cobalt exchanges in Na-kaolinite and Na-illite vide expressions in eqn. 3, exchange isotherms were plotted and are given in Figure 1. The isotherms were of Lang-

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms of Cobalt on Sodium-kaolinite and Sodium-illite at different temperatures.

- Kaolinite (25°)
- Kaolinite (50°)
- -○- - Illite (25°)
- -●- - Illite (50°)

muir type and their deviation from the diagonal indicated a strong preference for sodium as compared to cobalt both by kaolinite as well as illite. An examination of the isotherms further revealed that the affinity of cobalt for Na-kaolinite was greater than for Na-illite. Further the affinity was affected by temperature, being higher at 50° as compared to 25° in kaolinite and in a reverse order in illite.

Values of selectivity quotients (K_c) were calculated vide eqn. 4. Plots of $\log K_c$ against equivalent ionic fractions of cobalt are given in Figure 2. Using the trapezoidal rule the areas under these curves were utilised for calculating the values of equilibrium constants for the reactions in kaoli-

nite and illite at 25° and 50° and are given in Table 1. In the exchange in Na-kaolinite the value

Fig. 2. Logarithms of Selectivity Quotients vs. Equivalent ionic fractions of Cobalt in kaolinite and illite,

- Kaolinite (25°)
- Kaolinite (50°)
- -○- - Illite (25°)
- -●- - Illite (50°)

of the equilibrium constant at 50° was higher than 25° indicating a higher preference for cobalt as compared to sodium in kaolinite at the high temperature. The values followed a reverse order at the two temperatures in illite. The results were in accordance with the deductions drawn from the exchange isotherms.

An examination of Table 1 further revealed that the free energy changes (ΔG°) during the reactions were positive. These were indicative of a non-spontaneity of exchange in the direction of cobalt in both the clays. The difference in the values of free energy changes at 25° and 50° was much greater in the case of exchange on illite than in the case of kaolinite. The enthalpy changes (ΔH°) were in accordance with temperature dependant exchanges, the reaction being endothermic during cobalt exchange on Na-kaolinite and exothermic during its exchange on Na-illite. Thus cobalt was more strongly bound on illite and less strongly bound on kaolinite in comparison to sodium. The release of cobalt in illitic sodic soil process may not, therefore, be so easy as in the case of kaolinitic sodic soils. These results found support from entropy changes during the exchanges. Thus the greater disorder indicated by positive entropy effects during cobalt exchange on Na-kaolinite was in accordance with the low strength of binding of cobalt on kaolinite as a result of an extended diffuse distribution of cobalt ions in the electrical double layer. On the other hand, negative entropy changes during cobalt exchange on Na-illite were in accordance with a greater strength of binding of cobalt to fixed specific sites on the illite surface producing a greater order in the system.

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